

Twenty-two *X. campestris* bacteriophages were classified as having five phage strains: TBP₁, TBP₂, TBP₃, TBP₄, and TBP₅ (Table 2). Forty isolates were classified by their susceptibility to those phage strains into eight bacterial strains, A-H. Phage strains TBP₁ and TBP₂ were the most widely distributed, and bacterial strain A was most susceptible to all phage strains. Strain H was not susceptible. Bacterial strain A could be widely attacked where samples were taken. Bacterial strains A and D can be used as indicators for all phage strains dominant in those areas (Table 1). □

Table 2. Classification of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* based on bacteriophage sensitivity in Thailand.

Bacterial strain	Phage strain					Bacterial isolates obtained
	TBP ₁	TBP ₂	TBP ₃	TBP ₄	TBP ₅	
A	+	+	+	+	-	TB 8206, 8208, 8209, 8234, 8202, 8212, 8214, 8216, 8218, 8230
B	+	+	-	+	-	TB 7536, 8004, 8104, 8204, 8205, 8211, 8221, 8236
C	+	-	+	-	-	TB 8210, 8227, 8228, 8233
D	+	-	-	-	+	TB 8203, 8222, 8223, 8225, 8226
E	-	+	-	+	-	TB 8201, 8207, 8213, 8217, 8219, 8224, 8235, 8301
F	-	-	+	-	-	TB 8215, 8231, 8232
G	-	+	-	-	-	TB 8229
H	-	-	-	-	-	TB 8003

Nitrogen fertilization and sheath rot (SR) development in rice

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SR, caused by *Sarocladium oryzae*, was identified in Bangladesh in the early 1970s. It has become a constraint to N-responsive modern varieties (MV).

We studied the effect of 0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha on SR severity in transplanted aman BR11, an MV, and Nizersail, a local improved variety. Recommended cultural practices were followed, including 65 kg P and 45 kg K/ha at final land preparation. Urea N was applied in equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with 4 × 3-m plots and raised levees.

At early booting, all tillers of 10 randomly selected hills/plot were inoculated with *S. oryzae* cultured on sterilized rice grains. The grain inocula were pushed

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1. ShR disease index 0-9 scale. Left to right: 0 = healthy and 9 = severe ShR development. Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Disease index (DI)

2. Relationship between N fertilization and ShR severity in B11 and Nizersail during t. aman. Dhaka, Bangladesh.

partly into the middle portion of the flag leaf sheath and held there with scotch tape. At maturity, disease intensity (DI) was rated using a 0-9 scale. Zero indicated

no infection and 9 indicated complete flag leaf sheath discoloration and un-emerged panicles (Fig. 1).

Increasing N application significantly

increased DI in both varieties (Fig. 2). The regression coefficient (b) in both varieties was equal, indicating a similar trend. □

Reaction to rice tungro virus (RTV) complex as influenced by insect pressure

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We inoculated five IR varieties with 1, 5, 10, 20, and 30 *N. virescens* per plant to test their reaction to RTV complex. The

insects were allowed 4-d acquisition access time on plants infected with both rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). Test plants were planted singly in clay pots and enclosed in mylar cages. One month after planting, insects were allowed 24 h inoculation access time on the plants. The second youngest leaf from each plant was

sampled for RTBV and RTSV by latex test 1 mo after inoculation.

Infection with RTBV and RTSV increased in IR36 and IR42 when viruliferous insects/plant increased from 1 to 30. Only RTBV infection increased in IR50 and IR54, whereas an almost equal infection of both RTBV and RTSV, and RTBV alone was obtained in IR56 (see figure).

Varieties infected only by RTBV (IR50 and IR54) may not serve as virus source because the virus could not be recovered by the vector insect. However, these test varieties may not be immune to RTSV infection (see table). □

Percentage infection of IR varieties when inoculated with RTSV at 1 insect/seedling, IRRI.

Variety	Inoculated seedlings (no.)	Infected seedlings	
		No.	%
IR36	36	21	58.3
IR42	38	15	39.4
IR50	38	6	15.7
IR54	38	8	21.0
IR56	39	32	82.0
TN1	102	85	83.3

Reaction of IR varieties to RTV complex when inoculated with varying numbers of viruliferous insects per plant, IRRI.

Evaluation of National Screening Nursery (NSN) and international Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) trials for bacterial blight (BB) and stem rot (SR) resistance

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We evaluated NSN and IRON varieties for BB, kresek, and SR resistance in kharif 1980, 1981, and 1982.

Each variety was planted in two 5-m-long rows. Plants were inoculated with kresek at 20 d after transplanting (DT) and with BB at 45 DT. Inoculation was by cutting 5 cm of the upper leaves with a sickle dipped in inoculum prepared by soaking small pieces of naturally infected leaves in water for 20 min. Infection was scored on a 1-9 scale.

SR screening was done under natural incidence, and evaluated at maturity on a

1-5 scale.

BB intensity was high in most trials. SR incidence was high only in 1982. Resistant entries were selected and re-tested. Entries with consistent reaction to SR and BB for 2 yr or longer are given in the table.

Sixteen NSN and 14 IRON entries were consistently resistant. Resistant IRON entries BR171-2B-8, IR13420-6-3-3-1, IR19660-131-3-3-3-3, IR9763-11-